

Nonseasonal ARIMA Modeling and Forecasting of Malaria Cases in Children under Five in Edum Bansa Sub-district of Ghana

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Author's contribution

The sole author designed, analyzed and interpreted and prepared the manuscript.

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Abstract

Approximately sixty-nine percent of deaths globally resulting from malaria infection occur in children under five years of age [1]. National control and prevention strategies will be greatly enhanced through better ability to forecast future trends in the disease incidence. This study sought to develop a five year forecasting model for malaria incidence among children under the age of five in the Edum Bansa sub-district of Ghana. A secondary monthly malaria incidence record data spanning the period of 2008-2013 was used to develop the model formulated. The Box and Jenkins ARIMA methodology was employed to obtain the best fitting model by comparing the normalized BIC, MAE and Stationary-R Square values, and Q-plots of residuals of the suggested models. Comparative analysis showed that ARIMA (1, 1, 2) has best performance. The five year forecast showed a linear trend angled diagonally up. This means malaria cases in children under five in the Edum Bansa sub-district of Ghana will increase steadily over the next five years (2013-2018). The high value of the Stationary-R Square 0.792 or 79.2% is an indication that 79.2% of the variation in the malaria cases can be explained by the data. The study suggests that the department of disease control and prevention in Ghana uses ARIMA (1, 1, 2) model to optimize malaria prevention by providing estimates on malaria morbidity among children under the age of five in the Edum Bansa sub-district.

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1 Introduction

Malaria is the fifth leading cause of death from infectious diseases in low-income countries. In Africa, malaria kills one child every 30 seconds and about 3,000 children every day. Over a quarter of all young child deaths in Africa occur due to malaria. Again, over one million people die from malaria each year (who are mostly children under five). Nine out of ten malaria cases occur in Sub-Saharan Africa. Pregnant women and their unborn children are particularly vulnerable to malaria, as a result of low birth weight and maternal anemia. Infants born to mothers with malaria are likely to have low birth weight which is the single greatest risk factor for death during the first months of life [2]. A number of studies have been carried out all over the world to reduce the impact of the disease by forecasting the disease so as to help in timely planning, and in enhancing preventive and control measures. In a work that aimed at comparing the performances of ARIMA, Neural Network and Linear Regression models for the prediction of Infant Mortality Rate, Purwanto et al. [3] compared the models using performance measures such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), using the Infant Mortality Rate data collected in Indonesia during the years 1995-2008. The results showed that the Neural Network Model with 6 input neurons, 10 hidden layer neurons and using hyperbolic tangent activation functions for the hidden and output layers was the best among the different models considered. Lin et al. [4] used time series analysis to investigate the relationship between the falciparum malaria in the endemic provinces and the imported malaria in the non-endemic provinces of China. An autoregressive integrated moving average model was first fit to the predictor variable. Of all the models tested, the seasonal ARIMA (1, 1, 1) and (0, 1, 1) model for malaria incidence fitted the data best according to the AIC and goodness-of-fit criteria [4]. Briet et al. [5] formulated a model for short term malaria prediction in Sri Lanka. The best model for forecasting and forecasting error varied strongly among the districts. For instance, in the district of Ampara, the best model was ARIMA (2, 1, 1). In other districts, ARIMA (0, 1, 2) was the best model [5]. Contreras et al. [6] developed a model for predicting the 'next-day' electricity prices in mainland Spain and California markets using an ARIMA model. Their developed model was able to forecast the 24 market clearing prices of tomorrow. The ARIMA model is an effective tool for forecasting time series [6]. Takyi Appiah et al. [7] modeled malaria cases in the Ejisu – Juabeng municipality of Ghana. Their objectives were to find the best fitting model and to forecast for the next two years. Five suggested models were developed such as ARIMA (1,1,0), ARIMA (1,1,1), ARIMA (2,1,2), ARIMA (0,1,1) and ARIMA (2,1,1). The best model was ARIMA (2, 1, 1) and was selected based on the fact that it had the smallest normalized BIC, smallest absolute mean error and biggest stationary R-square. The forecast was found to have an oscillatory trend for some period and then remained constant for the period of two years [7]. A fairly accurate time series model could predict several years in the future, this being an advantageous skill when planning future requirements [8]. National control and prevention strategies will be greatly enhanced through better ability to forecast future trends in the disease incidence. To this end, it is therefore imperative to develop a predictive model for malaria patterns for the period of five years in Edum Banso sub- district of Ghana.

2 Problem Statement

In Ghana, 3.5 million people contract malaria every year. Approximately 20,000 children die from malaria every year (25 per cent of the deaths of children under the age of five). Even if a child survives, the consequences from severe malaria such as convulsions or brain dysfunction can hamper long-term development and schooling. The annual economic burden of malaria is estimated 1-2 percent of the Gross Domestic Product in Ghana. A malaria-stricken family spends an average of over one quarter of its income on malaria treatment, as well as paying prevention costs and suffering loss of income. Malaria-afflicted families on average can only harvest 40 percent of the crops harvested by healthy families. In endemic areas, as much as 60 percent of children's schooling may be impaired as a result of repeated bouts of malaria. Malaria-endemic countries are among the world's most impoverished. The cost of malaria control and treatment slows economic growth by about 1.3 per cent a year in Africa [2]. Edum Banso (one of the four sub-districts

in the Mpohor district of Ghana) which is located in the western region is known to have high crude death rate (CDR). The CDR of 9.1 of Mpohor district is higher than the 6.2 for the western region of Ghana which is very alarming. With malaria being the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in the district, it impedes economic growth and long term development of the district. This is because it is the major cause of student and employee absenteeism and the decreased level of productivity that the district continues to experience. With 64% of the population of the district engaging in Agriculture where the most predominant cash crops are cocoa and oil palm, the extent of economic loss cannot be underestimated. This loss robs the country of some percentage of its Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The overall labor force is weakened by the disease, aside the pain, suffering and uncertainty associated with it. Poor families and people in the rural areas are mostly at higher risk due to lack of resources to seek proper treatment of the disease even in complicated and life threatening cases [9]. Although Insecticide Treated Nets (ITN's) provide a cost effective means of ameliorating the effects of malaria, this measure will be expensive if large human populations must be protected in the district. Hence the need to analyze, monitor and predict the pattern of the disease in the district, so as to come up with a measure to curb the spread of the disease.

2.1 Significance of the study

The potential implication of this study is that by developing forecasting models for predicting the expected number of malaria cases in advance, timely prevention and control measures can be effectively planned like eliminating vector breeding places, spraying insecticides, and creating public awareness. The study will additionally enable policy makers and relevant stakeholders to foresee and allocate appropriate resources to maintain a steady decrease of the spread of the disease.

2.2 Objectives of the study

The objectives of this study were:

1. To model the under-five malaria morbidity rate for Edum Bansa sub- district using the Box - Jenkins (ARIMA) methodology.
2. To use the best model selected to predict the under-five malaria morbidity rate for Edum Bansa over a period of five years.

2.3 Scope and limitation

The scope of this study is restricted to the Edum Bansa sub- district of Ghana. The study and its outcome apply only to children below the age of five in the Edum Bansa sub- district of Ghana. The study was structured in the confines of the study matter. The researcher relied on secondary data (malaria cases of children below the age of five from Edum Bansa sub -district) from the Mpohor district hospital.

3 Methods

The study made use of monthly malaria cases report for the Edum Bansa sub-district. The data was obtained from Mpohor district hospital. The data covered periods from January 2008 to December 2013. Malaria incidence in Edum Bansa was forecasted using autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) models in order to build a predictive tool for malaria surveillance. The order of nonseasonal model represented by ARIMA (p,d,q) describes autocorrelation over a maximum order of p months; differencing order of d adjacent months and moving averages process order of q months. The Box and Jenkins approach was used to determine the patterns best describing the malaria time series. Malaria incidence time plot was made to detect and fix issues of non-stationarity. After achieving stationarity, models of varying orders were fitted, and compared using normalized Bayesian information criterion (BIC), mean absolute error (MAE), and Stationary-R Square. Autocorrelation function (ACF) which evaluates the correlation between the time series data and Partial autocorrelation function (PACF) which shows the correlation between the autoregressive

coefficients in different time lags were used to determine the parameters of the ARIMA model. The correlation values fell within the confidence limit which was set for the ACF and PACF; an indication of acceptable forecasting ability. ACF and PACF graphs of normalised data were used in the determination of the parameters p and q of the ARIMA model. Trial and error method was used to determine the final structure of the forecasting model. The model with the least BIC, MAE and the highest Stationary-R Square was selected for forecasting purpose. Data analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel (windows 10) and IBM SPSS STATISTICS (2015), V23.0, SPSS Inc.

3.1 Time series

To understand the elements in a time series, the analyst must consider the mathematical relationships among the various components. The most widely used model for time series decomposition is the multiplicative model, in which the series is analyzed as the product of its components. The model is :

$$Y = T \times C \times S \times I$$

Where

- Y = Actual value of the variable of interest
- T = Secular trend
- C = Cyclical component
- S = Seasonal component
- I = Irregular component

In the equation, Y is the product of four elements acting in combination to produce the series. The secular trend is the long-term component that represents the growth or decline in the time series over an extended period of time. The cyclical component is the wavelike fluctuation around the trend. The seasonal component is a pattern of change in quarterly or monthly data that repeats itself from year to year. The irregular component is a measure of the variability of the time series after the other components have been removed. An approach widely known as the Box-Jenkins methodology uses both the autoregressive and moving average techniques for forecasting. This methodology does not assume the presence of a particular pattern in the historical data of the series to be forecast. Instead, the Box-Jenkins technique, credited to George Box and Gwilym Jenkins, uses an iterative approach of identifying a potentially useful model from a general class of models. The selected model is then checked against the historical data to see if it accurately predicts the series. The model fits well if the residuals between the forecast value and the historical data points are small, randomly distributed independent. If the specified model is not satisfactory, the process is repeated using another model designed to improve on the original one. This process is repeated until a satisfactory model is found. Once a series has been identified as being stationary, the appropriate form of the ARIMA model is identified through examination of a correlogram containing the sample autocorrelation coefficients. Sample partial autocorrelation coefficients are also a computer program used to identify the appropriate ARIMA model. Once the model has been selected, a computer program uses a nonlinear least squares procedure to estimate the model coefficients. As a final step in the model selection process, diagnostic checking of the residuals takes place to determine whether the model is appropriate. This is accomplished through examination of a correlogram containing the sample autocorrelations of the residuals. If none of the autocorrelations is significantly different from zero, it is assumed that the sample residuals are independent with mean 0, and the model is deemed adequate. The Box-Jenkins methodology is a very powerful tool for providing accurate short-range forecasts. However, it is quite complex, requiring extensive computer analyses to perform the numerous computations required for identifying the model, estimating the parameters, and verifying that the model is adequate. To build a satisfactory model requires a great investment in terms of the analyst's time and computer resources. Also, analyst should always remember that the more complicated the forecasting model, the less likely its results are to be understood and accepted by management and used in the decision-making process.

4 Results and Discussion

From Fig. 1 the periodic fluctuations in the time plot is an indication of a trend of a strong monthly effect. By studying the graph of correlogram reveals a time dependent mean which is a characteristic of a time plot lacking stationarity. It also shows a property of homoscedasticity making the variance a function of time (since the spikes vary in amplitude) which is also typical of a time plot that lacks stationarity. It can also be inferred from Fig. 1. that the spread generally becomes closer as time increases, making the covariance of the time plot to lack stationarity. The series exhibits random walk behavior and need to be transformed before forecasting can proceed.

Fig. 1. Residual plot for units (ARIMA (0, 0, 0) with a constant

Fig. 2 (a)

Fig. 2 (b)

Fig. 2. ARIMA (0, 0, 0) with a constant

The autocorrelation plot in Fig. 2 (a) and Fig. 2 (b) show a very slow linear decay which is a key feature of a non-stationary series. Since the series initially shows strong positive autocorrelation, a non-seasonal difference will reduce the autocorrelation. The ACF also can be said to have decreased slowly. Non-seasonal differencing of the series will help stationarize the series. The first (and most important) step in fitting an

ARIMA model is the determination of the order of differencing needed to stationarize the series. Normally the correct amount of differencing is the lowest order of differencing that yields a time series which fluctuates around a well-defined mean value whose autocorrelation function (ACF) plot decays fairly rapidly to zero, either from above or below. If the series still exhibits a long term trend, or otherwise lacks tendency to return to the mean value, or if its autocorrelations are positive up to a high number of lags (like 10 or more), then it needs a higher order of differencing.

Fig. 3 (a)

Fig. 3 (b)

Fig. 3. ARIMA (0, 1, 0) with a constant

Figs. 3 (a) and (b) show that after the first non-seasonal differencing, the lag-1 autocorrelation was negative. The mean appears to have been stabilized. At this stage, it can be said that the series has no trend, periodicity and outlying observation any longer in the data, an indication of meeting a stationary condition.

Fig. 4 (a)

Fig. 4 (b)

Fig. 4. ARIMA (0, 2, 0) with a constant

Figs. 4 (a) and (b) show that the second order non-seasonal differencing has further increased lag 1 autocorrelation to a more negative direction which is a clear sign of over differencing (also an increase in the standard deviation). Hence there is the need to choose the first differencing for the model estimation.

4.1 Model identification

From Table 1, we observe the presence of the presence of moving averages models MA (0), MA (1), and MA (2), through the autocorrelation function. And the presence of autoregressive models AR (0) and AR(1) through the partial autocorrelation function, and for more accuracy in reconciling the best model among Box-Jenkins models, possible models of ARIMA (p, d, q) have been applied , and calculation of BIC, MAE and Stationary R-square are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1. Suggested models

Model	Normalize BIC	Stationary-R Square	MAE
ARIMA (1,1,2)	4.993	.794	8.810
ARIMA (1,1,0)	5.339	.795	10.818
ARIMA (1,1,1)	5.360	.793	10.806
ARIMA (0,1,1)	5.470	.70	11.077

From Table 1, ARIMA (1, 1, 2) was identified as the best forecast model. ARIMA (1, 1, 2) means autoregressive process of order 1, differencing of order 1 and moving average of order 2.

ARIMA (1, 1, 2) was selected as the best model as it had the least BIC and MAE. In addition, unlike the other three models, the Q plot of its residuals of ARIMA (1, 1, 2) was normally distributed and had mean of zero. As well, it passed Ljung-Box chi-square test.

4.2 Diagnostic checking of module

A residual in forecasting is the difference between an observed value and its forecast based on the observations. It can be observed from Fig. 5 that the residuals are uncorrelated and that the residuals have mean of zero. This is an indication that the formulated model is a good forecasting model.

Fig. 5. Graph of Noise residual of the series

The goodness of fit of the model was confirmed using the Ljung-Box test of goodness of the model. The null hypothesis could not be rejected at 5% level of significance with Ljung-Box test p-value 0.782. It was therefore confirmed and concluded that ARIMA (1,1,2) model was best fit for the series of the monthly malaria cases of under five children in Edum Banso sub-district.

Table 2. Model statistics

Model	Number of predictors	Model statistics											Number of outliers
		Stationary R-squared	R-squared	RMSE	MAPE	MAE	MaxAPE	MaxAE	Normalized BIC	Ljung-Box Q(18) Statistics	DF	Sig.	
Edum-Banso UFModel_1	0	.794	.618	11.787	11.075	8.810	33.592	37.403	4.993	12.705	17	.756	0

Table 3. ARIMA model parameters

				Estimate	SE	t	Sig.
EdumBansoUF-Model_1	EdumBansoUF	No transformation	Constant	-.029	.030	-.942	.349
			AR Lag 1	-.495	.110	-4.483	.000
			Difference Lag 1	.690	9.012	.077	.939
			MA Lag 2	-.587	3.725	-1.158	.875
			Month No Transformation Numerator Lag 0	-.002	.003	-.608	.545

4.3 Arima model parameters

On the assumption of normality of the series residuals, Maximum Likelihood Estimate technique was used to estimate the parameters of the model. From Table 3 the model can be formulated with their respective parameter estimates.

The second order moving average process is given by:

$$MA(2): X_t = \varepsilon_t - \theta_1\varepsilon_{t-1} - \theta_2\varepsilon_{t-2}$$

The first order Autoregressive process is given by:

$$AR(1): X_t = \varepsilon_t + \alpha_1X_{t-1}$$

The first order non-seasonal difference process is given by:

$$ARIMA(0,1,0): X_t - X_{t-1} = \mu$$

Hence the general form of ARIMA (1, 1, 2) is given by:

$$X_t = \mu + \alpha_1X_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t - \theta_1\varepsilon_{t-1} - \theta_2\varepsilon_{t-2}$$

Where

μ is the mean term

t is the indexes time

α_1 is the estimated Autoregressive parameter for lag 1

θ_1 is the estimated Moving average parameter for lag 1

θ_2 is the estimated Moving average parameter for lag 2

ε_t is the random error component at time t

ε_{t-1} is the previous value of the residual

$$\alpha_1 = -0.495$$

$$\mu = -0.029$$

$$\theta_1 = 0.690$$

$$\theta_2 = -0.587$$

The ARIMA (1, 1, 2) is:

$$X_t = -0.029 - 0.495X_{t-1} - 0.690\varepsilon_{t-1} + 0.587\varepsilon_{t-2} + \varepsilon_t$$

The forecast model as represented above is represented by the figure below:

The forecast in Fig. 6 shows a linear trend angled diagonally up. This means malaria cases in children under five in the Edum Bansa sub-district of Ghana will increase steadily over the next five years (2013-2018).

Fig. 6. Shows the five year forecast of malaria

5 Conclusions

Early prediction of malaria is very important for its control and intervention. This can reduce the huge effect of morbidity and mortality caused by the disease. National control and prevention strategies will be greatly enhanced through better ability to forecast future trends in the disease incidence. The model provides the means to better understand malaria dynamics in a resource-limited context with minimal input, yielding forecast that can be used for public health planning at the sub-district level. The monthly malaria incidence record of children below the age of five in Edum Banso has been studied using the Box-Jenkins (ARIMA) model methodology. A monthly malaria incidence record spanning the period of 2008-2013 for Edum Banso Municipality has been used to develop the model formulated. The performance of the resulting successful ARIMA model was evaluated by using the BIC, MAE, and the Stationary-R Square. The data was non-stationary and became stationary after the first order differencing. The first order differencing was chosen over the second differencing since the second order differencing showed signs of over differencing. The five year forecast showed a linear trend angled diagonally up. This means malaria cases in children under five in the Edum Banso sub-district of Ghana will increase steadily over the next five years (2013-2018). The high value of the Stationary-R Square 0.792 or 79.2% is an indication that 79.4% of the variation in the malaria cases can be explained by the data.

6 Recommendation

Based on the results of this study, it is recommended that the formulated model should be taken seriously by government, Health related Non-Governmental Organizations and policy makers to enable them administer adequate and timely malaria control and preventive measures to the Edum Banso sub -district.

Again, the study suggests that the department of disease control and prevention in Ghana uses ARIMA (1, 1, 2) model to optimize malaria prevention by providing estimates on malaria morbidity among children under the age of five in the Edum Banso sub-district.

Competing Interests

Author has declared that no competing interests exist.

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